

Role of extract purification in iron complexation and photo-Fenton reactivity under mild pH conditions

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ABSTRACT

Photo-Fenton processes operated at circumneutral pH require iron-complexing agents able to maintain Fe(III) solubility while sustaining efficient Fe(III)/Fe(II) cycling. In this work, polyphenol-rich extracts obtained from grape-processing residues were evaluated as natural ligands for photo-Fenton degradation of a mixture of six emerging contaminants (30 mg L⁻¹ total) at pH 5–7 using 5 mg L⁻¹ Fe(III). Raw alkaline extracts and membrane-refined fractions (300 and 150 kDa) were comprehensively characterized (TOC, COD, AOS, DLS, TPC, flavonoids and EEM fluorescence) and correlated with iron stability and degradation performance through a Doehlert multivariate design. Membrane fractionation significantly modified extract functionality. The 300 kDa retentate exhibited the highest phenolic and flavonoid densities (0.181 and 0.175 mg mg C⁻¹, respectively) and maintained soluble iron at pH 7 with minimal losses over 60 min. Under optimized conditions (pH 6, 16 mg C L⁻¹, stoichiometric H₂O₂), this fraction achieved 80% pollutant removal in 60 min, approaching the performance of EDTA and NTA when compared at equivalent carbon loads. In contrast, the raw extract was penalized by non-functional organic matter, while the 150 kDa fraction showed reduced chelating efficiency due to lower coordination-site density. The novelty of this work lies in establishing a direct correlation between membrane-driven compositional tuning (AOS and fluorescence signatures), iron stability, and photo-Fenton efficiency, demonstrating that functional group density rather than total organic carbon governs performance. These results highlight the potential of agro-residue-derived polyphenolic extracts as sustainable iron-complexing agents for photo-Fenton processes at mild pH.

1. Introduction

The Fenton process is one of the most widely studied advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) for water treatment and potential water reuse [1,2]. Its effectiveness relies on the generation of hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$) through the catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) by iron species. Hydroxyl radicals are highly reactive oxidants due to their unpaired electron, which drives rapid and non-selective reactions with organic pollutants that conventional wastewater treatment technologies cannot fully degrade [3–5]. The classical Fenton mechanism is described by Eqs. (1) and (2). In Eq. (1), Fe²⁺ catalyzes H₂O₂ decomposition to generate $\cdot\text{OH}$, becoming oxidized to Fe³⁺, whereas Eq. (2) represents the regeneration of Fe²⁺ via the reaction between Fe³⁺ and H₂O₂, producing hydroperoxyl radicals (HOO \cdot), which are less reactive than $\cdot\text{OH}$ [6]:

Although cyclic, the overall process is limited by the slow reduction of Fe³⁺ back to Fe²⁺, making Eq. (2) the rate-limiting step. This limitation can be minimized by irradiating the solution since its reaction kinetics is enhanced by UV-visible irradiation. Fe(III) species undergo ligand-to-metal charge transfer (LMCT), accelerating the Fe(III)→Fe(II) reduction and giving rise to the so-called photo-Fenton process [7]. In acidic media, Fe³⁺ forms Fe(OH)²⁺ (Eq. (3)), which photo reduces to Fe²⁺ while generating additional $\cdot\text{OH}$ (Eq. (4)):

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According to references, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ shows an active absorption band extending to slightly above 500 nm [8]. Although photo-Fenton substantially enhances reaction rates compared to dark Fenton, its optimal performance is restricted to strongly acidic pH (≈ 2.8). Above this value, ferric ions readily hydrolyze to form ferric hydroxides and oxyhydroxides, highly insoluble and catalytically inactive species that inhibit iron availability and shut down the catalytic cycle [9,10].

For this reason, operating the process at circumneutral pH requires iron-ligand complexes able to keep iron soluble and reactive while still enabling efficient $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ cycling. Therefore, suitable ligands must simultaneously prevent iron inactivation and promote the reduction of $\text{Fe}(\text{III})$ to $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$ —either thermally or photochemically [11].

This dual function is essential for sustaining $\cdot\text{OH}$ production at pH 5–7 and has traditionally been achieved with synthetic chelating agents such as EDTA, EDDS or NTA [12]. The general reactions are shown in Eqs. (5) and (6):

However, strong synthetic chelates tend to persist in natural waters and soils, raising environmental concerns [13–15]. Consequently, there is growing interest in natural organic ligands—including humic substances, phenols, polyphenol and flavonoids—which can form $\text{Fe}(\text{III})$ complexes of intermediate stability while remaining biodegradable [16, 17].

Recent life cycle assessment (LCA) studies have identified the mandatory acidification and subsequent neutralization steps of conventional photo-Fenton as its main sustainability bottleneck, due to the additional chemical consumption and sludge generation associated with pH adjustment [18]. In this context, iron-complexing strategies that enable operation at circumneutral pH directly address this limitation, potentially improving the overall environmental profile of the process. When combined with renewable, agro-residue-derived ligands, such approaches further align photo-Fenton technology with circular and resource-efficient treatment schemes [19].

Natural chelating agents derived from agro-industrial residues have emerged as sustainable alternatives to synthetic ligands for photo-Fenton processes at mild pH. Extracts from olive mill wastes or compost have shown the ability to stabilize $\text{Fe}(\text{III})$ while sustaining photochemical $\text{Fe}(\text{III})/\text{Fe}(\text{II})$ cycling. Polyphenol-rich extracts obtained through simple solid–liquid extraction have shown promising chelating behavior [20–22]. Their application not only enables photo-Fenton treatment at mild pH, but also integrates naturally into circular-economy strategies, since iron–organic complexes present in treated waters may later contribute to soil fertilization.

The valorization of agro-industrial residues within a circular bioeconomy framework has been widely discussed, highlighting the transformation of abundant waste streams into added-value products and bioactive compounds, thereby contributing to waste minimization and resource efficiency [23]. Different agro-industrial residues may yield extracts with distinct iron-chelating behaviors due to differences in phenolic composition and functional group density. For instance, olive mill wastes—already explored in previous photo-Fenton studies—are typically rich in simple phenolic acids whereas grape residues contain higher proportions of polyhydroxylated flavonoids and tannins, providing multiple coordination sites for $\text{Fe}(\text{III})$ [24]. Consequently, the choice of biomass source can significantly influence iron stability and photochemical reactivity.

In this context, the present work addresses a key unresolved question in natural ligand-assisted photo-Fenton systems: how does extract composition, and specifically membrane-driven fractionation, influence iron stability and photochemical performance at circumneutral pH?

Herein, polyphenol-rich extracts derived from grape-processing residues are subjected to sequential ultrafiltration (300 and 150 kDa) to tailor their supramolecular structure and functional group density.

Unlike previous studies that focus primarily on extraction yield or overall degradation performance, this work systematically correlates (i) average oxidation state, (ii) phenolic and flavonoid density normalized to carbon, (iii) fluorescence EEM signatures, and (iv) iron stability with photo-Fenton efficiency through multivariate experimental design.

By integrating compositional analysis, iron speciation and carbon-normalized performance comparison with commercial chelators, this study demonstrates that the effectiveness of natural ligands is governed by the density and organization of redox-active functional groups rather than by total organic carbon. This approach provides mechanistic insight into how membrane purification reshapes extract functionality and establishes design criteria for sustainable natural chelating agents operating at mild pH.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Model pollutants, Acetaminophen (ACF), acetamiprid (AMP), amoxicillin (AMX), caffeine (CAF), carbamazepine (CMC), clofibrac acid (CFB), commercial chelating agents namely ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) and Nitrilotriacetic Acid (NTA) and, model compounds, quercetin and, gallic acid were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich as high-purity grade reagents (>98%). Ethylenediamine-N,N'-disuccinic acid (EDDS) was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich as trisodium salt solution ($\sim 35\%$ in H_2O). Humic acids were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich as sodium salt. Iron (III) nitrate ($\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9 \text{H}_2\text{O}$) (>99%), aluminum chloride (AlCl_3) (>99%), and iron (III) chloride (FeCl_3) (>99%) were also supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2 , 30% w/w), sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4 , 96% w/w), and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) (>98%), were obtained from PanReac AppliChem. HPLC-grade methanol, formic acid, and acetonitrile were also supplied by PanReac AppliChem. Fertilizer HLS was supplied by Alfredo Iñesta S.L. as a mixture of humic extract (humic and fulvic acids), organic matter, nitrogen, and potassium.

2.2. Extraction of organic compounds from grape bagasse

Grape bagasse was selected as the working agricultural waste and was supplied by local winemaking companies from the eastern side of Spain. The extraction conditions (0.1 M KOH, pH 13, 24 h stirring at room temperature) were selected based on previous reports indicating enhanced solubilization of polyphenolic and humic-like components from lignocellulosic residues under alkaline conditions. [25] 125 g of wet residue was introduced in 0.5 L of KOH 0.1 M, and it was left in a paddle stirrer for 24 h.

Once the extraction was completed, the extracts were filtered with cellulose filters of 1,2 μm pore diameter to remove all the insoluble waste still present, i.e. grape seed, and refined using 300 and 150 kDa membranes, choosing both retentates as the refined extracts. Both membranes used were made of ceramic material, supplied by Tami Industries. Filtration was carried out with a constant flow rate of 4 $\text{L}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ at a pressure of 2 bars.

The 300 and 150 kDa ceramic ultrafiltration membranes were selected following fractionation strategies previously applied to humic-like substances from agro-industrial residues [21]. In these systems, separation depends on the hydrodynamic size and supramolecular aggregation of organic assemblies rather than on the molecular weight of individual molecules. The 300 kDa membrane was intended to retain larger polyphenol- and humic-like aggregates, while the 150 kDa membrane allowed comparison with a fraction containing smaller and more oxidized structures, enabling assessment of how extract refinement affects iron complexation and photo-Fenton performance.

2.3. Photochemical reactions

Photochemical experiments were carried out at room temperature in

a cylindrical open Pyrex reactor (7 cm diameter, 9.5 cm height), loaded with 250 mL of the solution. Conditions for each experiment are specified in their respective section. Irradiation was performed with a solar reactor, equipped with a xenon lamp, which emission spectrum imitates the solar one. Solar simulator (Oriel Instrument 81160) equipped with 300 W xenon short arc lamp was used as an irradiation source for the experiments.

2.4. Experimental design

The main objective of this work is to understand both the capabilities and the limitations of the extract. For this purpose, an experimental design based on a three-factor Doehlert matrix was used. The Doehlert experimental design was selected due to its efficiency in exploring multivariable systems with a reduced number of experiments while maintaining uniform precision in the experimental domain. This response surface methodology has been successfully applied in Fenton and photo-Fenton processes to identify the most influential operational parameters, improve understanding of system behavior and determine optimal working conditions [26]. The Doehlert design was used to assess the influence of pH (5–7), complexing agent concentration ([CA], 4–16 mg C L⁻¹), and H₂O₂ dosage (from the stoichiometric amount up to twice this value) on pollutant degradation. These variables were selected due to their direct impact on iron speciation and radical production. In each run, pH was first adjusted, followed by addition of the complexing agent, Fe(III), and the corresponding H₂O₂ dose. pH was first adjusted and then the CA was introduced at the corresponding concentration. Then, a concentration of 5 mg L⁻¹ Fe(III), added as Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, was applied, and the pH and H₂O₂ were then corrected accordingly. Irradiation source was already described in the previous section, and samples were taken at different times, 0, 5, 10, 15, 30, 45 and 60 min. Statgraphics Centurion XVI was used for response-surface fitting by the least squares' method.

Although 5 mg L⁻¹ Fe(III) was used during the reaction step, this value corresponds to the operational concentration within the treatment unit and does not represent the final discharge concentration. In practical applications, downstream separation steps (e.g., sedimentation, filtration or pH adjustment) would be implemented to ensure compliance with regulatory limits for total iron in treated effluents. Furthermore, since iron precipitation is favored at circumneutral pH, residual iron removal is expected to be technically feasible.

A mixture of 6 CECs (ACF, AMP, AMX, CAF, CMC, CFB) was used as target pollutant: a mixture of pharmaceuticals and pesticides that are commonly found in WWTP outflows [27]. All of them were added always at a concentration of 5 mg L⁻¹, and their removal was followed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). Although the concentration employed (5 mg L⁻¹ per compound) is higher than typical environmental levels, which are generally found in the µg L⁻¹ range, it was selected to ensure reliable kinetic monitoring and reproducible comparison of operational conditions. The objective of this work was to evaluate mechanistic performance and process trends rather than to simulate real environmental concentrations.

The six target contaminants were dissolved directly in ultrapure water at the desired concentration. The complexing agent was then added, followed by Fe(III) and the corresponding H₂O₂ dose according to the experimental design.

2.5. Chemical analysis

Several analysis methods were carried out to identify the substances in the extract. The total organic carbon (TOC) in the different extracts was determined using a Shimadzu TOC-V_{CPH} Total Organic Carbon Analyzer equipped with a Shimadzu ASI-V autosampler. Chemical oxygen demand (COD) was used to determine the amount of oxygen required to oxidize the organic and inorganic matter present in the extracts. 3 mL of the extracts were pipetted into COD Tests provided by

Supelco (COD Test, photometric, 25–1500 mg L⁻¹ (COD), Spectroquant®) and left at 150 °C in a thermoreactor for 2 h, and then the absorbance was measured and compared with a calibration line.

The average oxidation state was then calculated with both TOC and COD following the Eq. (7) [28]:

$$\text{AOS} = 4 - 1.5(\text{COD}/\text{TOC}) \quad (7)$$

Where the value obtained defined how oxidized the carbon present in the extracts was, being a value between -4 (where the carbon is in its most reduced state) and +4 (where it is fully oxidized). In addition, light scattering (DLS) was used to determine the size distribution (ZETASIZER Nano series (Nano-ZS)). In order to gain further insight into the structural composition of the extracts, excitation emission matrices (EEMs) were employed. The obtained matrix is processed via the EEMlab extension of MatLab, resulting in a 2D drawing of the different compounds present in the sample.

Phenolic compounds play an important role in this work so total phenolic content (TPC) was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu method as explained by Singleton et al. [29]. The same goes for the flavonoids, which may also be an important factor in this work. The concentration was determined via AlCl₃ method defined by Woisky et al. [30].

The concentration of each CEC was determined by HPLC (Hitachi Chromaster chromatograph; VWR) equipped with a UV/Vis detector. As stationary phase, a Prevail Hichrom column (C18-Select; 250 × 4.6 mm; 5 µm). The mobile phase with a flow rate of 1 mL·min⁻¹ was a binary mixture of solvents A (acetonitrile) and B (10 mM formic acid (aq)). The linear gradient was from 10% A to 90% A in 25 min. Re-equilibration time was 7 min. The wavelength used to follow the CECs was 225 nm. Retention times in the program were: amoxicillin (6.1 min), acetaminophen (9.3 min), caffeine (10.1 min), acetamiprid (13.8 min), carbamazepine (16.5 min) and clofibrac acid (24.5 min). The cumulative remaining concentration of pollutants (ΣC, where C is the concentration of every single pollutant) was used as response, as a mean to minimize the individual behavior of each target compound. Removals were expressed as relative values (Σ(C/C₀)), where C₀ is the initial concentration of pollutants.

Additionally, the concentration of iron species in water was measured using the standardized 1,10 phenanthroline spectrometric procedure (ISO 6332:1988). Measurements were conducted with a UV-VIS Spectrophotometer (UH5300 Hitachi Spectrophotometer) using a quartz cell featuring a 1 cm optical path length.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization

In order to have a better knowledge of the extracts several measurements were done and compared with those obtained with some organic matter model compounds as: humic acid, a commercial fertilizer based in humic like substances, gallic acid (reference for phenolic compounds) and quercetin (reference for flavonoids). Table 1 summarizes the results obtained from TOC, COD, AOS, DLS, and the concentration of phenolic and flavonoid content expressed as milligrams of gallic acid or quercetin per milligram of organic carbon of the sample. A more detailed composition of raw extract is shown in Supplementary Information (Table S1).

The results summarized in Table 1 demonstrate that both the alkaline extraction conditions and the subsequent membrane purification steps not only affect the total amount of extracted organic matter, but also significantly modify the relative abundance of redox-active functional groups, as evidenced by the phenolic and flavonoid contents normalized to carbon.

The raw extract obtained at pH 13 shows high TOC and COD values and a strongly negative average oxidation state (AOS ≈ -2), indicating

Table 1

Extracts and model compounds characterization.

Sample	TOC (mg C L ⁻¹)	COD (mg O ₂ L ⁻¹)	d (nm)	Phenolic conc. (mg GAE mg C ⁻¹)	Flavonoid conc. (mg FLA mg C ⁻¹)	Average oxidation state of carbon
Raw	7 188	28,400	676	0.146	0.120	-1.93
Refined 300 kDa	7 084	19,500	357.23	0.181	0.175	-2.01
Refined 150 kDa	582.92	1 192	194.88	0.049	0.098	+ 0.93
Fertilizer HLS	286,700	916,000	408.88	-	-	-0.79
Quercetin	-	-	-	-	-	+ 0.27
Gallic Acid	-	-	-	-	-	+ 0.57
Commercial HA	-	-	242.1	-	-	+ 0.8

the predominance of reduced, high-molecular-weight organic structures [28]. However, its phenolic and flavonoid contents relative to TOC are moderate, suggesting that a substantial fraction of the extracted carbon corresponds to non-phenolic organic matter, carbohydrates or aliphatic moieties, which do not directly contribute to iron complexation and may act as radical scavengers or light absorbers during photo-Fenton treatment [31].

After purification with the 300 kDa membrane, TOC remains high while COD decreases, resulting in a slightly more reduced AOS. More importantly, this fraction exhibits the highest phenolic and flavonoid ratios per unit of carbon among all the extracts. This indicates a selective enrichment of polyphenol- and flavonoid-rich macromolecular structures, likely associated with humic-like substances and lignin-derived fragments. The increase in these ratios demonstrates that ultrafiltration does not simply concentrate organic matter but rather enhances the relative abundance of functional groups capable of coordinating Fe(III) and promoting ligand-to-metal charge transfer (LMCT) under irradiation.

In contrast, the 150 kDa retentate displays a pronounced decrease in both phenolic and flavonoid contents normalized to TOC, together with a positive AOSC value. This suggests that the second purification step preferentially removes or dilutes polyphenolic structures, yielding an extract dominated by more oxidized, low-molecular-weight compounds

with limited metal-chelating ability. While some flavonoids may still be present, their lower relative abundance implies a reduced density of catechol-like or hydroxylated aromatic sites per unit of carbon.

Comparison with reference compounds further highlights these trends. Simple phenolic acids such as gallic acid exhibit higher oxidation states but a well-defined phenolic structure, whereas commercial humic-like substances show intermediate AOS values but lower normalized phenolic contents. The 300 kDa extract combines a low oxidation state with the highest phenolic and flavonoid densities, a combination that is particularly favorable for stabilizing soluble Fe(III) complexes while maintaining sufficient photoreactivity.

3.2. Fluorescence excitation-emission matrices (EEMs)

Fluorescence excitation–emission matrices provide qualitative insight into the nature and relative abundance of fluorophoric organic structures present in the extracts and reference compounds, allowing comparison of compositional changes induced by membrane purification and their relationship with functional performance [32].

The raw extract (Fig. 1A) exhibits a complex fluorescence pattern with multiple overlapping regions. A pronounced signal at low emission wavelengths ($\lambda_{Em} \approx 300\text{--}350$ nm) and excitation around 270–290 nm is consistent with the presence of protein-like and aromatic amino

Fig. 1. Comparative fluorescence EEM of natural extracts and model compounds: Raw extract (A), extract refined by a 300 kDa membrane (B), extract refined by a 150 kDa membrane (C), gallic acid (D), quercetin (E), humic acids (F) and fertilizer humic-like substances (G). The x-axis corresponds to excitation wavelength ($\lambda \approx 250\text{--}550$ nm), while the y-axis represents emission wavelength ($\lambda \approx 300\text{--}600$ nm).

acid-related fluorophores commonly extracted under strong alkaline conditions. In addition, a broad fluorescence band extending toward higher emission wavelengths ($\lambda_{Em} \approx 400\text{--}500\text{ nm}$) indicates the presence of humic-like substances, typical of agricultural residues and lignin-derived materials [33]. The coexistence of these signals suggests that the raw extract contains a chemically heterogeneous mixture in which potentially photoactive polyphenolic structures coexist with a substantial fraction of non-functional organic matter.

After purification with the 300 kDa membrane (Fig. 1B), a clear modification of the fluorescence landscape is observed. The intensity of the protein-like region is markedly reduced, indicating the partial removal of nitrogen-containing and highly labile organic compounds. At the same time, fluorescence attributed to phenolic- and flavonoid-like structures becomes more distinguishable, generally observed at excitation wavelengths around $\lambda_{Ex} \approx 250\text{--}300\text{ nm}$, with emission regions at $\lambda_{Em} \approx 300\text{--}400\text{ nm}$ for polyphenols and $\lambda_{Em} \approx 500\text{--}600\text{ nm}$ for flavonoids. This relative enrichment is consistent with the increased phenolic and flavonoid contents normalized to TOC reported in Table 1 and supports the selective retention of high-molecular-weight, aromatic and polyphenol-rich structures during ultrafiltration. The persistence of humic-like fluorescence further suggests that these macromolecular assemblies remain dominant in this fraction.

In contrast, the 150 kDa retentate (Fig. 1C) shows a substantial overall decrease in fluorescence intensity across all regions. The humic-like and polyphenolic signals are strongly attenuated, indicating that a significant fraction of the fluorophores retained in the 300 kDa fraction is either removed or diluted during the second purification step. The remaining fluorescence appears weaker and less structured, in agreement with the lower phenolic content and more oxidized nature of this extract inferred from AOS values. This confirms that the 150 kDa fraction is dominated by smaller, more oxidized organic molecules with limited aromatic conjugation and reduced capacity to act as effective iron-complexing ligands.

The EEMs of the reference compounds provide further context for these observations. Gallic acid (Fig. 1D) displays very weak fluorescence, as expected for a small, highly oxidized phenolic acid with limited conjugation. Quercetin (Fig. 1E) shows a more defined fluorescence signal in the flavonoid region, confirming its strong aromatic and polyhydroxylated character. Commercial humic acids (Fig. 1F) present a broad but relatively low-intensity humic-like signal, while the humic-like fertilizer (Fig. 1G) exhibits a strong and intense fluorescence band centered in the humic region, indicative of a highly conjugated, aromatic-rich structure.

When compared collectively, these matrices reveal that the 300 kDa extract most closely combines features of natural humic-like substances and flavonoid-rich structures, while avoiding the excessive protein-like contribution observed in the raw extract. This compositional balance explains why this fraction exhibits superior iron-chelating stability and photo-Fenton performance: it contains a high density of aromatic hydroxylated groups capable of Fe(III) coordination and LMCT-driven photoreduction, while minimizing non-functional organic matter that could act as radical scavengers or light filters.

Overall, the EEM analysis confirms that membrane purification not only reduces organic load, but also selectively reshapes the fluorophoric composition of the extracts, enriching photoactive polyphenolic structures in the 300 kDa fraction and explaining the marked differences observed in iron stabilization and contaminant degradation efficiency.

3.3. Stability of the iron chelate

The stability of Fe(III) complexes formed with the different extracts was evaluated at pH 5, 6 and 7 and compared with EDTA as a standard chelating agent (Fig. 2). The temporal evolution of soluble iron provides direct insight into the ability of each organic fraction to maintain iron in a soluble and reactive form under circumneutral conditions, a prerequisite for effective photo-Fenton operation.

Fig. 2. Comparison of the Fe(III) concentration at the beginning of the experiment (0 min) and after 60 min for the extracts and EDTA at different experimental pH conditions: pH 5, 6 and 7.

The raw extract exhibits the lowest initial concentration of complexed iron and a pronounced decrease after 60 min at all tested pH values. This limited stability is consistent with the compositional features identified in Sections 3.1 and 3.2. Although the raw extract contains polyphenolic structures, Table 1 shows that their phenolic and flavonoid contents normalized to TOC are only moderate, while EEM analysis reveals a significant contribution from protein-like and other labile organic fluorophores. These components may compete with effective ligands for iron coordination, forming weak or transient complexes, and may also promote side reactions that destabilize Fe(III) in solution. As a result, iron progressively hydrolyzes or precipitates, particularly at higher pH values, leading to a rapid loss of soluble iron.

In contrast, both membrane-purified extracts show a markedly improved iron-chelating performance. The 300 kDa retentate displays high initial concentrations of soluble Fe(III) and minimal losses after 60 min, even at pH 7. This enhanced stability can be directly correlated with its low average oxidation state of carbon (AOS ≈ -2) and, more importantly, with the highest phenolic and flavonoid densities per unit of carbon (Table 1). The EEMs further confirm the enrichment of aromatic, polyphenol- and humic-like fluorophores and the removal of protein-like structures. Together, these features indicate a high density of hydroxylated aromatic sites capable of forming relatively strong yet photoactive Fe(III) complexes. Such complexes effectively suppress iron hydrolysis while remaining sufficiently labile to participate in ligand-to-metal charge transfer (LMCT), explaining both their high stability and their superior photo-Fenton performance observed in subsequent sections.

The 150 kDa retentate shows an intermediate behavior. While it is clearly more effective than the raw extract in maintaining iron in solution, a more pronounced decrease in soluble Fe(III) concentration is observed over time, particularly at pH 6 and 7. This behavior is consistent with its higher AOS and significantly lower phenolic content relative to TOC, indicating a dominance of smaller, more oxidized organic molecules. As suggested by the EEM analysis, the reduced aromatic conjugation and lower density of catechol-like functionalities limit the stability of the formed Fe–ligand complexes, which are more prone to dissociation or hydrolysis over time.

As expected, EDTA exhibits the highest iron stability across all pH values, showing minimal changes between 0 and 60 min. This reflects the formation of very strong Fe–EDTA complexes, which efficiently prevent iron precipitation even under near-neutral conditions. However, such strong binding is also known to reduce Fe(III) photoreactivity at

mild pH, as excessively stable complexes can hinder Fe(III)/Fe(II) cycling. In this context, the behavior of the 300 kDa extract is particularly relevant, as it achieves a favorable compromise between iron stabilization and dynamic redox cycling, a balance that is essential for sustained photo-Fenton activity.

In general, the iron stability trends observed in Fig. 2 seem fully consistent with the compositional and spectroscopic evidence discussed in Sections 3.1 and 3.2. Extracts enriched in reduced, polyphenol-rich, high-molecular-weight organic matter form the most stable and functional Fe(III) complexes, whereas extracts dominated by non-functional or highly oxidized organic carbon show limited chelating efficiency. These results highlight that iron stability in natural ligand-assisted photo-Fenton systems is governed not by total organic carbon, but by the density and nature of specific coordinating functional groups, particularly phenolic and flavonoid moieties.

3.4. Effect of operating variables on photo-Fenton performance (Doehlert design)

The influence of pH, complexing agent concentration ([CA]) and H₂O₂ dosage on the photo-Fenton degradation of the selected model pollutants mixture was evaluated using a three-factor Doehlert experimental design. This approach allowed identification of the dominant operational variables and their interactions for each type of extract, while accounting for the intrinsic chemical differences discussed in Sections 3.1–3.3. The degradation profiles of each individual contaminant corresponding to the central point of the Doehlert matrix are included in the Supplementary Information (Figure S1).

3.4.1. Raw extract

The response surface plots obtained for the raw extract (Fig. 3) show that pollutant removal is strongly dependent on pH and oxidant concentration, particularly at low H₂O₂ doses. The highest removal efficiencies are observed under acidic conditions and at relatively high extract concentrations, indicating that only a fraction of the organic matter present in the raw extract actively participates in Fe(III) complexation and photoactivation.

This behavior is consistent with the compositional features identified earlier. As shown in Table 1, the raw extract contains a large amount of organic carbon with only moderate phenolic and flavonoid densities, while EEM analysis revealed a significant contribution from protein-like and other labile organic components. These non-functional fractions likely compete with target pollutants for hydroxyl radicals and may absorb incident radiation, reducing photon availability for LMCT processes. Consequently, increasing extract concentration does not proportionally enhance performance and may even promote scavenging

effects.

As H₂O₂ concentration increases, the system becomes less sensitive to pH and extract dosage; however, the overall improvement remains limited. This suggests that oxidant availability alone cannot compensate for insufficient iron stabilization or inefficient Fe(III)/Fe(II) cycling when the ligand environment is dominated by non-specific organic matter.

The standardized Pareto chart (Fig. 4) confirms these trends. Although none of the individual effects cross the statistical significance threshold, pH and H₂O₂ concentration exhibit the strongest standardized effects, followed by interaction terms involving extract concentration. These results indicate that, for the raw extract, operational parameters can modulate performance only within a narrow window, and the extract primarily plays a secondary role in supporting iron activity under favorable conditions. The model presented a standard deviation of approximately 12%, which can be attributed to the heterogeneity of the raw extract.

3.4.2. Raw extract under dark Fenton conditions

Under dark Fenton conditions (Fig. 5), pollutant removal remains negligible across the entire experimental domain. Neither pH, oxidant concentration nor extract dosage produces a significant improvement, confirming that the raw extract is unable to sustain the Fenton cycle in the absence of irradiation.

This observation reinforces the mechanistic interpretation derived from Sections 3.2 and 3.3: although some Fe–ligand interactions may occur, the organic matter present in the raw extract does not efficiently promote Fe(III) reduction in the dark, and radical scavenging effects dominate. The model presented a standard deviation of approximately 5%. The standardized Pareto chart (Fig. 6) further confirms the lack of statistically relevant factors, highlighting the strictly light-dependent nature of the catalytic activity observed for this extract.

3.4.3. Extract refined by a 300 kDa membrane

A markedly different behavior is observed for the 300 kDa refined extract (Fig. 7). In this case, removal efficiency is strongly influenced by the combined effect of all three variables, with a clear dependence on pH and extract concentration at low oxidant doses.

At low H₂O₂ levels, high removal efficiencies are achieved at moderately acidic pH and intermediate extract concentrations, indicating the presence of a sufficient concentration of photoactive Fe–ligand complexes. This result is fully consistent with the compositional enrichment of polyphenols and flavonoids identified in Table 1 and with the dominance of aromatic, humic-like fluorophores observed in the EEMs. These structures provide multiple hydroxylated aromatic sites capable of stabilizing Fe(III) and promoting LMCT-driven

Fig. 3. Response-surface contours of elimination efficiency for the raw extract as function of pH and [CA], segmented by H₂O₂ concentration.

Fig. 4. Standardized Pareto chart for the raw extract, illustrating the importance and interaction effects (A: pH, B: [CA], C: H₂O₂) on the elimination efficiency.

Fig. 5. Response-surface contours of elimination efficiency for the raw extract in the ‘dark Fenton’ as function of pH and [CA], segmented by H₂O₂ concentration.

Fig. 6. Standardized Pareto chart for the raw extract in the ‘dark’ Fenton, illustrating the importance and interaction effects (A: pH, B: [CA], C: H₂O₂) on the elimination efficiency.

photoreduction, thereby sustaining efficient hydroxyl radical generation.

At higher oxidant doses, the reactive domain broadens; however, a plateau in removal efficiency becomes apparent at high extract concentrations, particularly above pH 5.5. This behavior suggests the onset

of parasitic reactions, such as radical scavenging by excess organic matter or inner filter effects, which limit further performance gains despite increased oxidant availability.

The model presented a standard deviation of approximately 9%, remaining below 10%, which indicates a satisfactory agreement

Fig. 7. Response-surface contours of elimination efficiency for the extract refined by a 300 kDa membrane as function of pH and [CA], segmented by H_2O_2 concentration by the photo-Fenton process.

between the experimental and predicted values. The Pareto analysis (Fig. 8) clearly identifies pH as the dominant variable, followed by extract concentration and interaction terms involving pH. This confirms that, even for optimized natural ligands, maintaining iron in a soluble and photoactive form remains the primary control factor, while excessive ligand concentrations may become counterproductive.

3.4.4. Extract refined by a 150 kDa membrane

The response surfaces obtained for the 150 kDa extract (Fig. 9) show a consistent but less pronounced dependence on extract concentration, with pH again emerging as the controlling variable. Increasing extract dosage improves performance under acidic conditions, indicating that this fraction still contains Fe-chelating compounds capable of supporting photo-Fenton reactions.

However, compared to the 300 kDa extract, the operational window is narrower and removal efficiencies are lower. This behavior correlates well with the lower phenolic and flavonoid densities and higher oxidation state of this fraction (Table 1), as well as with the weaker and less structured fluorescence signals observed in the EEMs. Although smaller aromatic molecules may still form Fe complexes, their reduced stability limits the persistence of active catalytic species, particularly at

higher pH.

The model presented a standard deviation of approximately 7%, indicating a good agreement between experimental and predicted values. The standardized Pareto chart (Fig. 10) confirms the predominance of pH, while the effects of oxidant and extract concentration remain secondary. This highlights that, for this extract, iron solubility rather than oxidant availability controls overall performance.

3.5. Comparison with commercial chelating agents and model compounds

To contextualize the performance of the natural extracts, pollutant degradation was compared with that obtained using commercial chelating agents (EDTA, EDDS and NTA), model phenolic and flavonoid compounds (gallic acid and quercetin), commercial humic acids, and humic-like substances used as fertilizer, under identical operating conditions. In all cases, comparisons were carried out at a fixed carbon input (14 mg C L^{-1}) to account for residual TOC considerations relevant to water reuse applications and to avoid uncertainties associated with stoichiometric calculations in complex organic matrices.

As shown in Fig. 11, the raw extract exhibits the poorest performance, even compared with the control experiment, due to competition

Fig. 8. Standardized Pareto chart for the extract refined by a 300 kDa membrane, illustrating the importance and interaction effects (A: pH, B: [CA], C: H_2O_2) on the elimination efficiency.

Fig. 9. Response-surface contours of elimination efficiency for the extract refined by a 150 kDa membrane as function of pH and [CA], segmented by H_2O_2 concentration by the photo-Fenton process.

Fig. 10. Standardized Pareto chart for the extract purified by 150 kDa membrane, illustrating the importance and interaction effects (A: pH, B: [CA], C: H_2O_2) on the elimination efficiency.

Fig. 11. Photo-Fenton removal of the mixture of the six target pollutants (5 mg L^{-1} each, 30 mg L^{-1} total concentration) with time. Elimination kinetics for the extracts and EDTA under the same operating conditions (pH 6, 5 mg L^{-1} Fe(III) , stoichiometric H_2O_2) with a carbon input of 14 mg C L^{-1} .

between non-complexing organic matter and target pollutants for $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals, as discussed in Sections 3.1 and 3.4. In contrast, both membrane-refined extracts show a substantial improvement in degradation kinetics, confirming that purification effectively removes non-functional organic fractions that hinder photo-Fenton efficiency. As expected, EDTA yields the fastest and most complete pollutant removal, reflecting its strong iron-chelating ability.

Fig. 12 further compares the 300 kDa extract with its main compositional analogs. Both gallic acid and quercetin exhibit rapid degradation kinetics, confirming the high photoactivity of well-defined phenolic and flavonoid structures. In contrast, commercial humic acids and fertilizer-derived humic-like substances display very limited activity, comparable to experiments without added ligands. These results indicate that not all humic-like materials are equally effective, and that the balance between aromaticity, functional group density and molecular organization is critical. It should be noted that the grape residues used in this study were fresh and had not undergone humification processes; therefore, the presence of mature humic substances in the extracts is expected to be low. The superior performance of the 300 kDa extract supports the conclusion that its activity arises from an optimal combination of polyphenolic and humic-like structures rather than from bulk humic content alone.

Comparison with commercial chelating agents at identical carbon doses (Fig. 13) shows that the 300 kDa extract approaches the

Fig. 12. Photo-Fenton removal of the mixture of the six target pollutants (5 mg L^{-1} each, 30 mg L^{-1} total concentration) with time assisted by the model compounds (quercetin, gallic acid, commercial humic acids and commercial humic-like substances) at pH 6 with 5 mg L^{-1} Fe(III), stoichiometric H_2O_2 , and a carbon dose of 14 mg C L^{-1} .

Fig. 13. Photo-Fenton removal of the mixture of the six target pollutants (5 mg L^{-1} each, 30 mg L^{-1} total concentration) with time assisted by the commercial Fe(III)-chelating agents at pH 6 with 5 mg L^{-1} Fe(III), stoichiometric H_2O_2 , and a carbon dose of 14 mg C L^{-1} .

performance of EDTA and NTA, reaching near-complete pollutant removal under the tested conditions. This highlights the ability of the natural extract to sustain efficient photo-Fenton activity at circum-neutral pH, despite its heterogeneous nature.

Experiments were conducted under more favorable molar conditions for each chelator, stoichiometric molar ratio 1:1, whereas the more efficient concentrations were selected based on the Doehlert experimental design. EDDS and NTA exhibit the fastest initial degradation, in agreement with their known photoreactivity at mild pH (Fig. 14). EDTA performs slightly slower, consistent with the formation of overly stable Fe-EDTA complexes that partially hinder Fe(III) photoreduction. Among the natural ligands, the 300 kDa extract clearly outperforms the 150 kDa fraction, in line with its higher phenolic and flavonoid content per unit carbon and its superior iron stability (Sections 3.1 and 3.3).

To finish, normalization of removal efficiency to carbon dosage (Table 2) provides a more realistic comparison of ligand performance.

Fig. 14. Photo-Fenton removal of the mixture of the six target pollutants (5 mg L^{-1} each, 30 mg L^{-1} total concentration) with time assisted by the commercial Fe(III)-chelating agents and natural extracts at pH 6 with 5 mg L^{-1} Fe(III), stoichiometric H_2O_2 , and optimal molar ratio, by the photo-Fenton process.

Although synthetic chelators exhibit higher normalized efficiencies, the values obtained for the natural extracts remain within the same order of magnitude. Although EDDS and NTA exhibited faster initial degradation kinetics, reaching almost complete removal within 30 min, final removal percentages after 60 min were used for comparison. This choice ensures that the evaluation accounts for both kinetic efficiency and the persistence of Fe(III)-ligand reactivity over the full treatment period. Considering their renewable origin, biodegradability and lower environmental persistence, these results demonstrate that polyphenol-rich extracts from grape residues represent a viable alternative to synthetic chelators for photo-Fenton applications at mild pH, particularly in contexts where sustainability and circular-economy considerations are prioritized.

Although the performance of polyphenol-rich natural extracts remains lower than that of optimized synthetic chelators, the results obtained in this study highlight their potential as sustainable complexing agents for photo-Fenton applications at mild pH. Their renewable origin, inherent biodegradability and reduced environmental persistence justify continued investigation of this approach, particularly to better understand the limits of their performance and to identify residual biomasses with more favorable compositions. Moreover, in many regions—especially in low- and middle-income countries—the availability and cost of synthetic chelating agents may represent a significant barrier to implementation. In such contexts, locally sourced agricultural residues could provide a more accessible and economically viable alternative, reinforcing the relevance of natural ligand-assisted photo-Fenton processes from both technological and socio-environmental perspectives.

To evaluate the potential persistence of the natural ligands under photo-Fenton conditions, Total Organic Carbon (TOC) was monitored after 60 min of irradiation. Significant mineralization of the extract was observed in all cases (Supplementary Information, Figure S2), confirming that the organic matrix undergoes partial oxidative degradation during the process. These results indicate that, unlike highly persistent synthetic chelators, the polyphenol-rich extracts do not remain structurally intact in solution and are progressively transformed under oxidative conditions.

Despite this partial mineralization, reusability experiments revealed that the iron-complexing capacity of the 300 kDa fraction was largely preserved over three consecutive photo-Fenton cycles (Supplementary Information, Figure S3). Iron stability and pollutant removal efficiencies remained nearly unchanged during these cycles, suggesting that

Table 2Relative removal efficiencies (%·mg C⁻¹) for natural extracts compared to commercial chelating agents.

Sample	Concentration	Fe (III) concentration (mg L ⁻¹)	Carbon dosed (mg C L ⁻¹)	Pollutant removal (%)	Relative removal efficiency (% mg C ⁻¹)
Refined 300 kDa	16 mg C L ⁻¹	5	16	80.45	5.03
Refined 150 kDa	16 mg C L ⁻¹	5	16	65.76	4.11
EDTA	Molar ratio (L:Fe) 1:1	5	10.75	89.75	8.35
EDDS	Molar ratio (L:Fe) 1:1	5	10.75	97.02	9.02
NTA	Molar ratio (L:Fe) 1:1	5	9.68	100	4.11

sufficient redox-active functional groups persist to sustain Fe(III)/Fe(II) cycling. This behavior indicates that the extract does not act as a persistent chelating agent in the treated water, while its structural heterogeneity and functional group redundancy allow maintenance of catalytic performance over repeated uses.

Finally, it must be considered that the performance of the system under real water matrices may be influenced by the presence of inorganic ions (e.g., bicarbonate, carbonate, chloride) and background natural organic matter, which can act as radical scavengers or affect iron speciation. Nevertheless, it should be considered that micropollutant concentrations in real WWTP effluents are typically in the $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ range, with the total concentration of organic microcontaminants often below $100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Therefore, although matrix complexity may introduce additional competition effects, the radical demand associated with target pollutants would be substantially lower than under the mg L^{-1} levels investigated in this study.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that membrane-driven compositional tuning of grape-residue extracts critically determines iron stability and photo-Fenton performance at circumneutral pH. The 300 kDa retentate exhibited the highest phenolic and flavonoid densities normalized to carbon (0.181 and $0.175 \text{ mg mg C}^{-1}$, respectively) together with a strongly reduced character ($\text{AOS} \approx -2.0$). This compositional profile enabled stable Fe(III) complexation up to pH 7, with minimal soluble iron losses after 60 min, and resulted in up to 80% removal of a six-contaminant mixture (30 mg L^{-1} total) under optimized conditions (pH 6, 16 mg C L^{-1} , 5 mg L^{-1} Fe(III)).

In contrast, the raw extract ($\text{AOS} \approx -1.93$) contained substantial non-functional organic matter, which promoted scavenging and inner-filter effects, limiting degradation efficiency despite high TOC. The 150 kDa fraction ($\text{AOS} \approx +0.93$) showed significantly lower phenolic density ($0.049 \text{ mg mg C}^{-1}$) and reduced iron-chelating capability, achieving only 65% removal under comparable conditions.

Comparison at equivalent carbon loads ($14\text{--}16 \text{ mg C L}^{-1}$) showed that the optimized 300 kDa extract approached the performance of EDTA (89.8%) and NTA (100%) after 60 min, highlighting that functional group density and supramolecular organization, rather than molecular uniformity, govern process efficiency.

A direct relationship between membrane fractionation, average oxidation state, fluorescence EEM signatures and Fe(III) stability was identified, linking extract chemistry with photo-Fenton performance through multivariate experimental design. These findings provide mechanistic insight into the role of polyphenolic functionality in iron stabilization and establish design criteria for the development of bio-based iron-complexing agents operating at mild pH.

The outstanding activity observed for quercetin further identifies flavonol-rich matrices as promising candidates for future development. Ongoing work will focus on mechanistic evaluation of pure quercetin and on the valorization of quercetin-rich agro-residues as highly efficient natural ligands.

Although a detailed techno-economic assessment was beyond the scope of this laboratory-scale study, ongoing research is addressing the scalability of the extraction and membrane refinement steps. In particular, life cycle assessment (LCA) and process-integration analyses are

being developed to evaluate the environmental and energetic implications of implementing agro-residue-derived ligands at larger scale. These studies will provide a quantitative framework for assessing the overall sustainability of the proposed approach.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

M. Cerdán: Funding acquisition, Data curation. **G. Mattarello:** Investigation, Data curation. **J. Arévalo:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **L. Santos-Juanes:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **A. Arques:** Resources, Conceptualization. **A.M. Amat:** Resources, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper: Lucas Santos-Juanes reports financial support was provided by European Commission. Lucas Santos-Juanes reports financial support was provided by Spain Ministry of Science Innovation and Universities. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jece.2026.122270](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2026.122270).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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